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SISTERS BUT NOT IDENTICAL TWINS: SOME CAUTIONARY NOTES ON ADOPTING FORENSIC ANTHROPOLOGICAL METHODS IN BIOARCHAEOLOGY

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ABSTRACT

Age-at-death, sex, and stature estimation from adult human skeletal remains lie at the core of bioarchaeological and forensic anthropological research. Several methods have been proposed for such estimations, with almost all of them being developed using modern documented skeletal collections. Therefore, unavoidably bioarchaeology largely adopts relevant methodologies from forensic anthropology. Applying these osteological age-at-death, sex, and stature estimation methods to archaeological skeletal remains relies on the inherently flawed assumption that biological processes are homogenous across time and space. This paper offers a brief review of some of the key methods bioarchaeology has adopted from forensic anthropology, stressing the limitations of blindly using methods developed based on contemporary assemblages on archaeological ones, but also on systematic efforts that have been made to address these limitations.

KEYWORDS: age-at-death estimation, bioarchaeology, forensic anthropology, sex estimation, stature estimation.

INTRODUCTION

Bioarchaeology examines human (mostly skeletal) remains from archaeological excavations (Larsen, 2015). The human skeleton, as a living tissue, dynamically responds to several stimuli throughout the lifetime. As such, it forms a repository of information regarding living conditions long after an individual's death. Among the key aspects of past life that may be studied via the examination of human skeletal remains are diet, health and disease, mechanical stress, demography, mobility and others (Nikita, 2017). As humans are biocultural beings, that is, their biological and sociocultural dimensions are inextricably linked, the interpretation of human skeletal data must consider the historical, natural environmental and cultural context which past individuals experienced. Through such an integrated approach, bioarchaeological studies can elucidate important topics, often with contemporary implications, such as social inequalities and their embodied outputs, adaptation to climate change, the factors underlying differential susceptibility to diseases, or the character and impact of past human mobility (Buikstra et al., 2022).

Forensic anthropology also examines human skeletal remains but of contemporary individuals. The key research question now is not how people lived but how they died (Byers, 2016). In specific, some of the key research questions are: What is the identity of the deceased? What is the cause of death? What were the circumstances of death? To answer the first question, emphasis is placed on methods of skeletal sex, age-at-death, ancestry and stature estimation. The second and third questions very often involve the study of different types of trauma (e.g. blunt-force, sharp-force), as well as taphonomic agents (natural or anthropogenic) that may have impacted the body peri- or post-mortem (Christensen et al., 2019).

Many of the key methods used by bioarchaeologists have been drawn from forensic anthropology. These methods revolve primarily around the key areas of forensic anthropological inquiry highlighted above: age-at-death, sex, and stature estimation. This is unavoidable since the development of relevant methods requires documented collections, that is, large skeletal collections whereby the age-at-death, sex, and stature of the deceased is well-known in advance (e.g. through medical records or coroner reports) (Petaros et al., 2021). Through access to such collections, one can examine normal skeletal variability and how it associates to sex and age differences. Subsequently, these observations are standardized in methods that allow scholars to assess the sex or age-at-death of an unknown skeleton based on its skeletal morphology and how this matches the patterns seen in the documented collection. Similarly, modern reference skeletal collections have been used to develop

metric standards for skeletal variation, such as metric sex estimation but also stature estimation. The latter provide an idea of how people looked in the past but, more importantly, convey information regarding physiological stress since individuals undergoing malnutrition or health insults during childhood often exhibit growth stunting. Note that ancestry estimation has a central place in forensic anthropology for individuation purposes, along with sex, age-at-death and stature estimation (though recently this has been criticized; DiGangi and Bethard, 2021). However, bioarchaeologists estimate instead so-called 'biodistances', which express phenotypic -morphological-similarity as a proxy for genetic affinities (Nikita, 2020). Thus, in this case, bioarchaeology is not directly adopting forensic anthropological methods.

This paper provides an overview of some of the key methods bioarchaeology has adopted from forensic anthropology for sex, age-at-death and stature estimation. Emphasis is placed on the limitations of blindly using methods developed based on contemporary assemblages on archaeological ones, but also on systematic efforts that have been made to address these limitations.

1. SKELETAL SEX ESTIMATION

1.1. Overview

Skeletal sex estimation is central in bioarchaeology as it offers key information regarding palaeodemographic patterns (e.g. fertility rates), mortuary practices (e.g. differential treatment of males and females post-mortem), sexual division of labour in past societies, different susceptibility of males and females to various diseases, and many others. By assessing past individuals' sex, one could also explore the association between biological sex and socially constructed gender in different contexts across time and space.

The assessment of sex based on skeletal remains employs morphological and metric methods. Such assessment is only performed for the remains of adult individuals because testosterone levels, the hormone largely responsible for the development of male physical characteristics, are overall very low before puberty. Therefore, there is only minimal skeletal sexual dimorphism in juveniles (O'Donnell et al., 2017; Wilson et al., 1981). Several methods for skeletal sex estimation in juveniles have nonetheless been proposed (e.g. Stull et al., 2020); however, their use has not been generalized and in some cases they have been found to give poor estimates when applied in different assemblages from those used to develop them (e.g. Lamer et al., 2021). Thus, such methods will not be discussed in this paper.

For adult skeletons, sex estimation is most often based on pelvic morphological traits because this anatomical area has evolved to accommodate different needs in males and females: bipedal locomotion in males; bipedal locomotion and parturition in females (Fischer and Mitteroecker, 2017; Huseynov et al., 2016). As such, the female pelvis is overall broader (Fig. 1), and exhibits an elongation of the pubic bone,

a ventral arc on the anterior surface of the pubic bone, a subpubic concavity on the ischio-pubic ramus, an ischio-pubic ramus ridge, a pre-auricular sulcus, and broader and shallower greater sciatic notches (Buikstra and Ubelaker, 1994; Phenice, 1969). Methods that combine in different ways multiple pelvic markers in sex estimation have been proposed by Klaes et al. (2012), Bruzek (2002) and other scholars.

Figure 1. Morphology of male and female pelvis (image from Nikita and Mardini (2022) distributed under a creative commons licence (CC BY-NC 2.0))

When the pelvis is not available, which is often the case in poorly preserved archaeological remains, sex estimation is based on cranial morphological traits (Fig. 2). Here, sexual dimorphism is based on the premise that males are generally larger and more robust than females, hence specific anatomical structures, especially where muscles attach, will be better developed in the former. These structures include primarily the glabella, supraorbital ridges, occipital protuberance, mastoid processes and mental eminence, which tend to be more pronounced in male skeletons compared to female ones (Buikstra and Ubelaker,

1994). In addition, the supraorbital margins tend to be sharp in females but rounded in males, while male mandibles have squarer chins and show gonial eversion and mandibular ramus flexure contrary to female mandibles that are more gracile with round chins and no or very slight flexure (Loth and Henneberg, 1996; Williams and Rogers, 2006; but see also Kemkes-Grottenthaler et al., 2002 and Oettlé et al., 2009). Approaches that combine multiple of these traits in sex estimation have been proposed, with most notable the work of Walker (2008).

Figure 2. Morphology of male and female cranium (image from Nikita and Mardini (2022) distributed under a creative commons licence (CC BY-NC 2.0))

Beyond morphological traits, skeletal sex estimation may adopt metric standards. These are based on the fact that males are generally larger than females, thus the dimensions of individual male bones should be larger than the corresponding female dimensions.

Measurements obtained from various bones are compared between sexes using univariate or multivariate statistical tests, depending on whether the comparison employs a single measurement/bone dimension

or multiple ones (e.g. Moore et al., 2016). More recently, metric sex estimation has started employing geometric morphometrics, that is, instead of obtaining linear measurements, scholars obtain landmark coordinates, which allows to control for the effect of size on the data by translating, rotating, and scaling the skeletal elements under study, thus facilitating the discrimination of males and females based on skeletal shape (Baca et al., 2022; Gillet et al., 2020). Metric methods have been developed for pretty much every skeletal element, such as the pelvis (Gonzalez et al., 2009), cranium (Gillet et al., 2020; Nikita and Michopoulou, 2018), long bones (Krüger et al., 2017) but also the hand and foot bones (DeSilva et al., 2014; Navega et al., 2015), sternum (Bongiovanni and Spradley, 2012) and others (Hou et al., 2012), with varying degrees of success.

1.2. Challenges and Prospects

Metric and morphological methods for sex estimation based on the pelvis show high accuracy rates worldwide, despite some inter-population variability in the degree of expression of the morphological traits and the extent of metric sexual dimorphism (e.g. Betti, 2014). Some adaptations have been made to accommodate for population specificity (Oikonomopoulou et al., 2017), but this is minimal so even the original methods designed for North American groups perform very well globally (Kenyhercz et al., 2017). This is to be expected since, as stated above, sexual dimorphism in the pelvis is linked to evolutionary processes aimed at accommodating distinct needs in males and females worldwide.

In contrast to the pelvis, sex estimation methods, metric and morphological, based on the cranium, long bones and other skeletal elements tend to be population-specific, even though levels of population-specificity in sexual dimorphism differ pending on the skeletal element examined (see for example Indra et al., 2021 for talus and patella standards). Population-specificity is because skeletal size and robusticity are largely controlled by the daily activities of different groups and these may differ considerably in different sociocultural environments (Eshed et al., 2004). In addition, human dimensions play an important role in thermoregulation and other adaptations to climatic conditions (Ruff, 1994); hence, again, skeletal size is highly population-specific as it depends on the natural environment different populations occupy and how they have adapted to it over successive generations.

To address the issue of population-specificity in cranial and post-cranial sexual dimorphism, forensic anthropologists have developed metric sex estimation standards based on different groups across the

world. As such, there are currently dozens of published metric standards (univariate and multivariate) for sex estimation using different elements for different populations worldwide (e.g. cranial metric sex estimation: Colombia - González-Colmenares et al., 2019; Japan - Ogawa et al., 2013; Australia - Franklin et al., 2013; Thailand - Patterson and Tallman, 2019; South Africa - Dayal et al., 2008). In addition, it is common practice to validate published standards for one population by applying them to different groups to test how they perform (Brůžek et al., 2017; Lewis and Garvin, 2016). Similarly, for morphological standards, there have been adaptations to sex estimation combining multiple traits in order to accommodate for different levels of inter-population robusticity (e.g. Oikonomopoulou et al., 2017 adapted the Walker, 2008 method for modern Greeks).

Correspondingly, bioarchaeologists try to use methods developed for populations geographically proximal to the archaeological groups they study in order to control as much as possible for inter-population variability, especially with respect to environmental adaptations. However, for archaeological remains, there is the additional serious complicating factor of secular changes in body size. Numerous studies in populations worldwide have shown that over time long bones have become more linear and gracile, pelvic breadth has been reduced while innominate height has increased, cranial vault and face dimensions have decreased, while the cranial base has been elongated (Langley and Jantz, 2020 and references therein). Moreover, daily lifeways differed greatly across time and this certainly affected the levels of robusticity of different populations; in addition, different groups exhibited different levels of sexual division of labor (Ogilvie and Hilton, 2011; Sofaer Derevenski, 2000), which would also affect the manifestation of skeletal sexual dimorphism in anatomical areas beyond the pelvis.

These issues are well known among bioarchaeologists but only rather recently have there been attempts to address them. A recent open access and open source web application, SexEst (Fig. 3), co-developed by one of the authors (E.N.) used metric data (cranial and postcranial measurements) from pre-industrial skeletons with a worldwide distribution to generate machine learning classification models for sex prediction (Constantinou and Nikita, 2022). As the developers of SexEst acknowledged themselves, this application has the limitation that in the skeletal collections used to develop the sex prediction models, sex was rarely documented but it was estimated skeletally, as expected given the date of these assemblages and the lack of associated medical or other data. Nonetheless, sex estimation had been based on morphological

characters of the pelvis, which have accuracies over 85%, often over 90% (e.g. Kenyhercz et al., 2017; Klales and Cole, 2017), as well as on cranial morphological traits, which have an accuracy around 80% (e.g. Krüger et al., 2015). Note that a recent study that developed sex prediction models using five cranial metric variables from the same collections as SexEst and tested them on a modern American assemblage achieved 86.26% correct sex classifications, which suggests that these pre-industrial undocumented samples have the potential to offer accurate sex predictions (Lescure et al., 2020). As the creators of SexEst stress ‘...using sex prediction equations based on pre-industrial assemblages conveys an important advantage to osteoarchaeologists, which outweighs the limitation that such equations are based on individuals with non-documented sex’ (Chrysostomou and Nikita, 2022, p. 10). A second distinct

characteristic of SexEst is that it does not provide ancestry- or population-specific equations for sex prediction but instead all equations are based on global samples. This approach agrees with the recent acknowledgment that population-specific sex prediction equations “are not as applicable in archaeological contexts, in which the geographical or genetic origin of individuals is rarely known...In this kind of context, a method that is not temporally or geographically limited by the sample used to create it is preferable...” (Lescure et al., 2020, p. 4). The performance of SexEst is currently being tested in a modern Greek skeletal assemblage; we hope that its open access and open source format will promote its use by scholars worldwide so that the accuracy of the predictions can be validated in assemblages of different ancestry and antiquity.

Figure 3. SexEst Home page (<http://sexest.cyi.ac.cy/>/ see also Constantinou and Nikita, 2022)

2. AGE-AT-DEATH ESTIMATION

2.1. Overview

Age-at-death estimation from skeletal remains is based on changes that occur on the skeleton with time (biological age). The rate of these changes may be affected by several factors such as activity, diet, and disease. Biological age is used by bioarchaeologists and forensic anthropologists as a proxy for chronological age, that is, the amount of time that has passed since the birth of the individual; however, biological and chronological age are not the same. Given the factors potentially affecting biological age and their cumulative action, chronological and biological age become increasingly divergent from each other, making the estimation of chronological age from biological age less precise for adults than for juveniles (Nawrocki,

2010). The following sections offer a brief overview of some of the key methods used in age-at-death estimation in juveniles and adults.

2.1.1. Juveniles

Appearance and Union of Ossification Centers: The ossification of the skeleton is initiated at specific centers. In the fetus there are 806 ossification centers but gradually several of these fuse together to form our mature skeleton, which consists of 206 bones. The appearance of these ossification centers can change considerably as they mature so it can be used as an age-at-death marker (Schaefer et al., 2008). In addition, the timing of the fusion of the ossification centers to form the mature bones is also an important age-at-death indicator as different centers fuse at different points in a juvenile’s life time (Cunningham et al.,

2016) (Fig. 4). Note that ossification center union often starts earlier in females than in males. Considering that the sex of juvenile skeletons cannot be accurately estimated, when using this age-at-death estimation method, the standards for both males and females should be adopted and age should be estimated with the appropriate margin of error.

Figure 4. Age of fusion of the epiphyses with the diaphysis at major appendicular joints (image from Nikita and Mardini (2022) distributed under a creative commons licence (CC BY-NC 2.0))

Long-Bone Length: From the fetal stage until all our ossification centers fuse together and our skeletal growth ceases, there is a strong relationship between long-bone length and age (Fazekas and Kósa, 1978). Based on this principle, a number of regression equations have been produced that allow the prediction of an individual's age (dependent variable) based on long bone length (independent variable) (Cunningham et al., 2016). As the growth rates differ between males and females, most regression equations are sex-specific. Since in archaeological juveniles sex cannot be accurately estimated, all available equations

should be used and the estimates from the two sexes should be combined.

Other Bone Dimensions: Beyond the length of the long bones, age-at-death for juveniles may be estimated using the dimensions of various skeletal elements, such as the pars basilaris of the occipital bone (Scheuer and MacLaughlin-Black, 1994), vertebrae (Kósa and Castellana, 2005), cranium and mandible (Smith et al., 2021), shoulder and pelvic girdles (Cardoso et al., 2017).

Dentition: The estimation of age-at-death based on the dentition is considered the most accurate approach as tooth formation and eruption follows a well-defined pattern. In particular, deciduous teeth start forming in utero, and most of them erupt in the mouth during the second year of an individual's life. Permanent teeth start forming during the first year of life, and they erupt in the mouth during childhood and adolescence (even in early adulthood if the third molars are examined) (Whittaker, 2000). The most straightforward approach for estimating age-at-death based on dental formation and eruption is the use of a dental atlas, that is, a reference chart depicting the stage of dental development that corresponds to different ages (Fig. 5). Different atlases are available in the literature; the ones most commonly seen in published studies are a) the Ubelaker (1989) atlas, which was based on tooth eruption data from Native Americans, other "nonwhite" groups, and white North Americans, whereas tooth formation data were derived primarily from white North Americans, as well as b) the London Atlas, which was based on collections at the Royal College of Surgeons of England and the Natural History Museum (London, UK), as well as dental radiographs of living individuals (AlQahtani et al., 2010). An alternative approach to atlases examines the developmental stage of individual teeth, and the biological age to which this developmental stage corresponds, and is based on charts or tables generated from modern data (e.g. Demirjian et al., 1973; Moorrees et al., 1963). Finally, instead of assessing the stage of tooth development qualitatively, certain studies have developed regression equations for age-at-death estimation based on tooth length (Liversidge et al., 1993; Liversidge and Molleson, 1999).

2.1.2. Adults

Fusion of Primary and Secondary Ossification Centers: Although most ossification centers fuse during childhood and adolescence, some centers fuse during early adulthood. These include, for example, the iliac crest and the medial clavicle (Webb and Suchey, 1985).

Morphology of the Pubic Symphysis: The pubic symphysis is where the two ossa coxae articulate at

the ventral part of the pelvis. In young adults, the pubic symphysis exhibits billowing; subsequently, a 'ventral rampart' forms, that is, an osseous epiphysis that begins fusing on the ventral part of the symphysis; later still, there is a rim around the margins of the pubic symphysis and billowing completely disappears; finally, the pubic symphysis surface and rim degenerate, micro- and macro-porosity form and the margins become irregular (Fig. 6). Various schemes have been proposed for the recording of these morphological changes and their association with biological age (e.g. Gilbert and McKern, 1973; Todd, 1920, 1921), with the most commonly used method being the Suchey-Brooks one (Brooks and Suchey, 1990).

Despite the wide application of this method, there is substantial overlap between the limits of successive stages, and it has been found to be inaccurate for individuals older than 40 years of age (Fleischman, 2013; Meindl and Russell, 1998). Several attempts have been made to refine it with emphasis on enhancing its accuracy for older individuals (e.g. Merritt, 2018a; Stoyanova et al., 2017). Nonetheless, the use of these revised methods has not been generalized in the literature and the original method by Brooks and Suchey (1990) remains the standard one, while a recent large-scale meta-analysis found the Suchey-Brooks method to be reliable and exhibit moderate-to-high accuracy (Schanandore et al., 2022).

Figure 5. Part of the London atlas (adapted from AlQahtani et al., 2010)

Figure 6. Metamorphosis of the pubic symphysis with age (image from Nikita and Mardini (2022) distributed under a creative commons licence (CC BY-NC 2.0))

Morphology of the Iliac Auricular Surface: Age-progressive morphological changes have also been identified on the iliac auricular surface. This surface is originally finely grain textured with regular billowing. Gradually, the granularity turns coarser, the billowing disappears, and there is microporosity. Eventually, the surface becomes dense and disorganized

and macroporosity forms. Different schemes have been proposed to capture these changes and their association with biological age with most common being the Lovejoy et al. (1985) and Buckberry and Chamberlain (2002) ones.

Suture Closure: The human cranium consists of several bones that gradually fuse together during

adulthood (Fig. 7). Proposed methods for age-at-death estimation based on the stage of fusion of the sutures, the interlocking joints between cranial bones, have considerable antiquity (e.g. Todd and Lyon, 1924). The most common method was proposed by Meindl and Lovejoy (1985) and it focuses on combinations of ectocranial sutures, that is, sutures visible on the outer surface of the cranium. Alternative methods have employed the palatal sutures (Hens and

Godde, 2020), the endocranial sutures (Buikstra and Ubelaker, 1994), or combinations of ectocranial, endocranial, and maxillary sutures (Nawrocki, 1998). Validation studies have shown that although cranial sutures do fuse with increasing age, the rate at which fusion occurs is too variable to allow accurate age-at-death predictions (Ruengdit et al., 2018; Xanthopoulos et al., 2018).

Figure 7. Gradual fusion of cranial sutures from left to right (image from Nikita and Mardini (2022) distributed under a creative commons licence (CC BY-NC 2.0))

Morphology of the Sternal Rib End: Age-progressive changes have also been identified at the sternal rib end, which is initially flat or billowy with rounded edges but gradually its rim becomes thinner and irregular, surface porosity develops, and it assumes an overall ragged appearance (Figure 8). The method

most commonly used to associate morphological sternal rib end changes with biological age is that proposed by İşcan et al. (1984). Validation studies of this method have produced mixed results (Muñoz et al., 2018; Richard et al., 2022), and attempts have been made to refine it (Merritt, 2018b; Yoder et al., 2001) but their use has not been generalized in the literature.

Figure 8. Sternal rib end metamorphosis (image from Nikita and Mardini (2022) distributed under a creative commons licence (CC BY-NC 2.0))

Dental Wear: In adults, dental formation and eruption has been completed (with the exception of third

molars, which generally erupt in young adulthood). However, the dentition may still be used in age-at-

death estimation by focusing on the degree of dental wear. In specific, the rate of molar wear can be calibrated using juvenile dentitions based on the principle that first molars erupt at the age of approximately 6 years, second molars at the age of 12 years, and third molars at the age of 18 years. Thus, the amount of wear visible on first molars when the second molars have just erupted indicates the wear accumulated within 6 years, while by the time the third molars erupt, the first molars will exhibit 12 years of wear, and the second molars 6 years of wear. After calibrating the rate of wear per population, the degree of observed molar wear can be used to estimate age-at-death (Miles, 1962). The use of dental wear as an age marker is rather rare in practice given that a large number of juveniles is required in order to calibrate the rate of wear per population, which is hardly ever available in archaeological assemblages. In addition, first, second and third molars do not wear at the same rate; the first molars accumulate wear a bit faster than the second ones, while the third molars wear at the slowest rate (Miles, 1962). Finally, calibrations based on juvenile data may not be accurate since adults have larger jaw muscles and increased mechanical loading, thus accelerated wear compared to juveniles (Whitaker, 2000). Indeed, validation studies of various dental wear age-estimation methods have questioned the accuracy of this approach (Faillace et al., 2017; Prince et al., 2008).

Lamendin method: Lamendin and colleagues (1992) proposed a method for the estimation of age-at-death employing single-rooted teeth based on periodontitis and root transparency recorded on the labial root surface. Prince and Ubelaker (2002) subsequently modified this method to account for sex and ancestry differences. Tests of these methods have given contradictory results (Foti et al., 2001; Garizoain et al., 2020; González-Colmenares et al., 2007). Among the limitations of applying such methods in archaeological remains is the fact that the extent of periodontitis is difficult (or even impossible) to accurately assess when there are no soft tissues preserved, while the burial of the bodies even for a few years can generate biased results due to the effect of the soil (De Angelis et al., 2015).

Histomorphometry: Quantitative aspects of bone histology have also been used in age-at-death estimation. Note that contrary to the macroscopic methods described so far, histomorphometry is a destructive method as it requires the sectioning of the skeletal elements. Relevant methods usually focus on the size, type and density of osteons, the size and number of Haversian canals, as well as cortical thickness, and they have been developed for different skeletal elements, mostly the long bones and the ribs (e.g.

Crowder et al., 2012; Stout et al., 1994). When applying histomorphometric methods, it is important to bear in mind that several factors may affect cortical bone remodeling rates and thus the expression of the histological variables and the subsequent age-at-death estimates. These parameters include sex (especially in older individuals as remodeling rates are affected by hormonal changes occurring with menopause in women), physical activity which tends to accelerate remodeling, pathological conditions such as metabolic diseases, and others (Gocha et al., 2018). As with other methods presented above, the validation of histomorphometric methods has given mixed but mostly cautionary results (García-Donas et al., 2021; Maggio and Franklin, 2019).

2.2. Challenges and Prospects

In what concerns juvenile age-at-death, a potentially confounding factor is the fact that the rate of skeletal maturity has changed over the years. For instance, a study on secular trends in skeletal maturity in South African children between 1962 and 2001 found that the skeletal maturity of white children advanced during this period by 3.4 months and 2.0 months for males and females, respectively, while black children in 2001 were advance of the 1962 cohort by an average of 9.7 months and 15.8 months (Hawley et al., 2009). Similar secular trends in skeletal maturation, associated with improved socio-economic conditions, have been identified in children across the world (e.g. Hsieh et al., 2013; So and Yen, 1990; review in Malina, 1990).

In bioarchaeological contexts this topic has been explored by Mary Lewis and her colleagues who have studied systematically the onset of menarche and puberty, key aspects in the study of biological maturation, in medieval populations. Lewis et al. (2016a) explored the age at which adolescents in medieval England (900–1550 CE) entered and completed the pubertal growth spurt, studying almost 1000 adolescent skeletons. The authors found that adolescents entered puberty at around 10–12 years, that is, at a similar age to modern children; however, the onset of menarche in girls was delayed, especially for those living in London. Similarly, medieval males attained complete maturation at a later age (21 years) compared to modern European males (16–18 years). The authors attributed the delayed development of medieval adolescents to the adverse living conditions, including poor diet, infections and physical labour. To test further this hypothesis, in another study Lewis et al. (2016b) explored the impact of chronic illness on the rate of puberty in adolescents from medieval England and found that 22.2% of the adolescents showed some delay in pubertal development. Interestingly, the percentage of individuals showing delayed development

whilst suffering from a chronic condition was 40%, whereas only around 20% of non-pathological adolescents showed delay, supporting the link between hardship and delayed pubertal development. Finally, exploring the trade-offs between growth and reproduction before and after the Black Death in adolescent females from medieval London, DeWitte and Lewis (2021) found that the mean age of post-menarcheal females increased from the Early to Late pre-Black Death periods but declined post-Black Death. Early menarche in turn resulted in lower limb length for these females (DeWitte and Lewis, 2021).

The above studies on living and archaeological assemblages highlight the impact of secular changes in skeletal maturity, associated with changes in the living conditions. The different rates in growth and development imply that age-at-death estimation methods for juveniles (e.g. epiphyseal union, long-bone length) developed based on modern populations almost certainly lead to biased age estimates when applied to archaeological samples where growth rates were different (Halcrow et al., 2007; Humphrey, 2000). The older the date of a bioarchaeological assemblage, the harder it becomes to explore the degree to which skeletal growth and maturation differed in the past compared to modern standards and subsequently somehow correct relevant biases in chronological age estimation.

Beyond secular changes, which express trends occurring across generations, important differences in growth patterns, which affect skeletal age estimation, occur among contemporary populations as well as among individuals within a population. As with secular changes, these differences are strongly linked to different living conditions that characterize different groups at an inter- and intra-population level (Golden and Golden, 1991). As mentioned in previous sections of this review, growing up in an adverse environment, characterized by malnutrition and/or exposure to diseases, will result in growth stunting (Allen, 1994; Lewit and Kerrebrock, 1997). Note that if living conditions ameliorate, catch-up growth may take place so the individual will eventually catch up with its peers (Wit and Boersma, 2002); however, with archaeological assemblages, it is very difficult to ascertain whether catch up growth occurred or what the extent of growth stunting was in the first place. As such, disadvantaged juveniles may appear younger than their chronological age due to growth stunting.

Studies have shown that adverse environments exert a stronger effect on skeletal development compared to dental development (Cardoso, 2007; Conceição and Cardoso, 2011). Therefore, a way to partly address secular trends and intra- and inter-population variability among contemporary populations in regards to growth patterns, would be to favor dental-

based age-at-death estimation methods for juveniles, as is common practice in bioarchaeology. Nonetheless, it must be stressed that secular trends have been also identified for dental development in several modern populations (e.g. Cardoso et al., 2010; Vucic et al., 2014), as has population-specificity in dental development rates (e.g. Adams et al., 2019).

As mentioned in the Overview section, a major issue in skeletal age-at-death estimation, particularly for adults, whether in bioarchaeological or in forensic assemblages, is the discrepancy between chronological and biological age. As a result of this discrepancy, age-at-death estimates based on skeletal morphological changes may be inaccurate given the high levels of inter-population but also inter-individual variability in the rate of skeletal degeneration, pending on activity/occupational patterns, genetic predisposition, dietary quality and many other factors. This issue becomes even more pronounced when methods developed based on modern skeletal assemblages are applied to archaeological populations, whereby the living conditions were different and this surely impacted the rate of skeletal degeneration, but to an unknown degree. Having said that, we should stress that a number of studies found no significant correlation between skeletal markers of mechanical stress (enthesal changes, cross-sectional geometric properties) and the rate of degeneration at the pubic symphysis or the iliac auricular surface, suggesting that although living conditions affect skeletal age-at-death estimation, their effect is not straightforward (Bertsatos et al., 2021; Campanacho et al., 2012).

A final serious limitation of age-at-death estimation, both for juveniles and adults, is so-called 'age mimicry'. As explained above, conventional age estimation methods predict chronological age based on the expression of various skeletal changes. Such methods employ regression models where chronological age is treated as the dependent variable (i.e. the variable being predicted). However, in such models the age interval and central tendency for the stage of skeletal changes reflect the age composition of the reference sample, that is, the skeletal collection used to develop the age-estimation model. This phenomenon results in biased age estimates when the method is used on assemblages with a different age composition to that of the reference sample, such as pre-industrial skeletons (Bocquet-Appel and Masset, 1982).

Bayesian statistics and Transition Analysis (TA) may address the age mimicry problem as they calculate the probability of an individual having made the transition from one skeletal change stage to the next at each age (Milner and Boldsen, 2012). More specifically, TA estimates the age of transition between successive stages of an age marker, whereas Bayesian approaches compute the conditional probability that the

skeletal remains are from an individual who died at a certain age given that the observed age marker falls under a specific stage. Note that in Bayesian analysis it is essential to know in advance the so-called prior distribution of ages-at-death. Whereas for forensic studies such distributions may be extracted from national mortality figures and other sources, similar information is not available for archaeological assemblages with the exception of very few rather recent ones (e.g. 17th-century Danish rural parish records used in the ADBOU software - Milner and Boldsen, 2012). A software which implements TA is Transitional Analysis 3 (<https://ta3info.com/>). This software is based on large skeletal assemblages from across the world and implements age prediction based on machine-learning approaches and skeletal traits that cover multiple parts of the skeleton (Milner et al., 2021). Transitional Analysis 3 is currently in beta testing and its accuracy has not yet been validated. Nonetheless, several validation studies already conducted on Bayesian statistics and Transition Analysis in skeletal age estimation have produced contradictory results with some finding that these approaches do not really improve age predictions compared to conventional methods (Ferrante et al., 2015; Nikita et al., 2018) or do so only minimally (Thevissen et al., 2010), while others found a clear benefit to using a Bayesian model (Kim et al., 2022). However, multiple studies stress the importance of selecting an appropriate informative prior that matches the assemblage under study when using transition analysis (Kim et al., 2022; Simon and Hubbe, 2021), which as explained above, is extremely challenging with archaeological remains.

As mentioned in the previous paragraph, Transitional Analysis 3 employs machine-learning and multiple skeletal markers in age prediction. A similar promising approach has been developed very recently (Navega et al., 2022). This approach is based on the application of deep random neural network models on over 60 skeletal traits across the skeleton. The authors reported merely ~6 years mean absolute error in the obtained estimates and provide a user-friendly software, DRNNAGE, for the implementation of this method. Note that given how recent this method is, it has not been validated yet in other assemblages.

3. STATURE ESTIMATION

3.1. Overview

Stature estimation based on skeletal remains may employ anatomical or mathematical methods. Anatomical methods measure the height of the skeletal elements that contribute to one's stature, that is, the talus and calcaneus (in articulation), tibia, femur, first sacral vertebra, all vertebrae (except for

the atlas), and cranium (**Figure 9**). Subsequently, they sum these measurements and add a correction factor for the missing soft tissues (Fully, 1956; Raxter et al., 2006). Further refinements of this method proposed a correction for supernumerary vertebrae (Raxter and Ruff, 2010), and solutions for skeletons missing selected elements (Auerbach, 2011). Among the strengths of anatomical methods is that they are little affected by inter-population and inter-individual variation in body proportions (associated with climatic, nutritional, genetic, and other factors), while age-related stature loss is partly controlled for by using available equations that include an age term (Raxter et al., 2006). Their robusticity to inter-population and inter-individual variation implies that anatomical methods can be used even with individuals of unknown sex and ancestry. An important limitation of these methods is that they require an excellent preservation of several skeletal elements, including bones that are rarely preserved intact in archaeological contexts (e.g. cranium, vertebrae). Thus, their applicability is limited.

Mathematical methods are based on the principle that there is a positive and often significant correlation between stature and bone dimensions (especially long bone lengths). These methods comprise of regression equations that can predict stature based on certain bone dimensions (e.g. Jeong and Jantz, 2016; Pomeroy and Stock, 2012). The equations have been developed based on modern cadavers where living stature can be measured rather accurately or obtained from the available records for the deceased. Subsequently, bone measurements are obtained, either directly on the bones or through radiographs, and equations are produced where stature is the dependent variable and one or more bone dimensions are the independent variables. Femoral length has been found to provide the most accurate stature predictions, likely because it is the element that contributes most to stature, followed by the tibia and humerus (Wilson et al., 2010). Although regression equations can employ multiple skeletal elements simultaneously (multiple regression), a problem of multicollinearity arises since many bone measurements are inter-correlated to each other (Mansfield and Helms, 1982). Contrary to anatomical methods, regression equations for stature prediction are population- and sex-specific; this is why the available in the literature equations to estimate stature cover different populations across the world and are separate for males and females. Since mathematical methods estimate stature using only one or a few bones, they are generally not as accurate as anatomical methods, which use all skeletal elements that contribute to stature; however, they are much more applicable to archaeological assemblages since even in poorly preserved remains, a few bones

are usually sufficiently well represented to allow obtaining the necessary measurements. Very importantly, even if long bones are fragmented and maximum lengths cannot be measured, there are available equations based on the dimensions of several other elements that tend to be preserved even in

very damaged assemblages (e.g. hand and foot bones; Cordeiro et al., 2009; Musgrave and Harneja, 1978), while there have been equations developed specifically for fragmented bones (Simmons et al., 1990).

Figure 9. Measurements used in anatomical stature estimation (image from Nikita and Mardini (2022) distributed under a creative commons licence (CC BY-NC 2.0))

3.2. Challenges and Prospects

Due to the preservation of the remains, bioarchaeologists use primarily mathematical methods. However, the relationship between stature and individual bones may exhibit substantial variability at an intra- and inter-population level, thus caution should be exerted in selecting the most appropriate equation each time. Although there have been studies that showed that generic equations that do not require an unknown individual to be assigned to a given population often provide better results than population-specific equations (Albanese et al., 2016), given inter-population variability in body dimensions and proportions, bioarchaeologists try to adopt equations produced based on modern assemblages geographically as proximal as possible to the archaeological assemblage under study. An issue that remains even after adopting this approach, however, is secular changes, which cannot be accounted for when using equations developed based

on modern populations. In specific, since the 19th century there has been a trend to increasing adult stature in most European countries (Cole, 2000). Similarly, an overall increase in stature has occurred in China from 1985 to 2010 (Chen and Ji, 2013), as well as in America (e.g. Texas from 1929-1931 to 1968-1972, Malina and Zavaleta, 1980; Guyana from 1910 to 1980, Wilson et al., 2019) and other parts of the world. However, there are cases where no significant positive secular trend in stature has been observed, likely due to poor economic and social development, as for instance among 20th century South Africans (Louw and Henneberg, 1997; Myburgh et al., 2017).

To address the issue of secular changes, a number of bioarchaeological studies have adopted a so-called 'hybrid approach' that allows the generation of regression equations from archaeological assemblages of non-documented stature. Based on this approach, the anatomical method is used to calculate the living stature. Subsequently, regression equations are obtained using the lengths of the long

bones (e.g. Auerbach and Ruff, 2010; Maijanen and Niskanen, 2010; Raxter et al., 2008; Ruff et al., 2012; Vercellotti et al., 2009). Our team has also applied this method, though using a modern documented collection, the Athens Collection, and with the aim of creating regression equations specifically for Greek assemblages (Nikita and Chovalopoulou, 2017). This approach allows the creation of population-specific standards for archaeological assemblages, largely overcoming the issue of secular changes and inter-population variability arising from using equations based on contemporary skeletal collections. However, the application of the hybrid approach requires large numbers of very well preserved skeletons per assemblage so that the anatomical method can be applied successfully to a representative number of individuals and allow the creation of a sufficient training dataset, which will be subsequently used for the generation of regression equations for stature prediction in less well preserved skeletons from the same assemblage. This is a serious limitation in archaeological assemblages where skeletal preservation, especially of elements such as the vertebrae, sacrum or entire cranium is very rare.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Bioarchaeology and forensic anthropology have distinct research questions with the former primarily

focusing on reconstructing past life and the latter exploring contemporary death. Nonetheless, they both largely rely on the study of human skeletal remains and they share several methods. These methods, especially the ones for sex, age-at-death and stature estimation, have been developed mainly by forensic anthropologists as they require modern documented skeletal collections. This paper reviewed the issues that arise from the adoption of such methods in bioarchaeology, especially issues related to secular trends and intra- and inter-population variability. Although these issues are known, they are hardly ever explicitly discussed in bioarchaeological case studies and instead methods are used as if they are equally valid for modern and ancient populations. A way to partly overcome these issues is to adopt methods based on modern assemblages geographically as proximal as possible to the archaeological ones under study. However, this does not overcome the limitation of secular trends. Bayesian statistics, transition analysis, the use of hybrid approaches for developing methods directly based on archaeological assemblages are some of the proposed ways to address pending issues, but they are effective only to a certain extent. Efforts are ongoing but certain limitations are almost impossible to fully overcome due to the nature of the archaeological remains. In any case, it is imperative to acknowledge these limitations and adopt methods with appropriate caution.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Conceptualization, E. N., M.E.C.; writing—original draft preparation, E. N.; writing—review and editing, M.E.C. Both authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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